

EJP SOIL
European Joint Programme

Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

Deliverable D4.1 Soil-related policy analysis

Due date of deliverable: M34
Actual submission date: 25.10.2024

GENERAL DATA

Grant Agreement: 862695

Project acronym: EJP SOIL

Project title: Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

Project website: www.ejpsoil.eu

Start date of the project: February 1st, 2020

Project duration: 60 months

Name of lead contractor: INRAE

Funding source: H2020-SFS-2018-2020 / H2020-SFS-2019-1

Type of action: European Joint Project COFUND

DELIVERABLE NUMBER:	D4.1
DELIVERABLE TITLE:	Soil-related policy analysis
DELIVERABLE TYPE:	Report
WORK PACKAGE N:	WP4
WORK PACKAGE TITLE:	Policy analysis
DELIVERABLE LEADER:	Agnieszka Klimkowicz-Pawlas
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DISSEMINATION LEVEL:	PU

Suggested citation:

Klimkowicz-Pawlas A., Jandl R., Altobelli F., Martelli A., Kuk L., Cousin I., Raudner A., Ay J.-s., Asins S., Weninger T., Ramler D. 2024. Soil-related policy analysis. EJP Soil Internal Project SERENA, Deliverable 4.1, pp. 49.

ABSTRACT

The SERENA Task 4.1 focused on analysing existing policies, needed indicators and assessing the relevance of SERENA indicators in current policies. For this purpose, a detailed review of a number of international documents (directives, strategies, conventions, initiatives) on soil policy was carried out and, in addition, recommendations from previous projects and reports were analysed.

It was checked which soil threats (STs), soil-based ecosystem services (SESs) and their indicators have already been included in policy measures and which ST/SES SERENA indicators are necessary for the correct implementation of the objectives and targets of these policies. Furthermore, the list of ST/SES indicators proposed in the SERENA project was subjected to stakeholder assessment, who identified the national policy needs in this regard. This allowed the identification of relevant indicators needed at different scales (international, EU, national) to characterise soil threats and soil ecosystem services.

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

- CAP Common Agricultural Policy
 EEA European Environmental Agency
 EU European Union
 EUSO European Soil Observatory
 GDP Gross Domestic Product
 GHG Greenhouse Gas
 MINOTAUR Modelling and mapping soil biodiversity patterns and functions across Europe
 MS Member State
 SDGs Sustainable Development Goals
 SERENA Soil Ecosystem seRvices and soil threats modelling aNd mApping
 SESs Soil-based ecosystem services
 SIREN Stocktaking for Agricultural Soil Quality and Ecosystem Services Indicators and their Reference Values
 SML Soil Monitoring Law
 SOC Soil Organic Carbon
 SSM Sustainable Soil Management
 ST Soil threat
 UNCCD United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification
 UNFCCC United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
 VGSSM Voluntary Guidelines for Sustainable Soil Management
 WP Work Package

1 Introduction and objectives

In recent years, there has been a significant increase in awareness that soils are an irreplaceable and non-renewable resource that provides a range of environmental and economic benefits to society (Baritz et al., 2021; Faber et al., 2022; Vanino et al., 2023; Keesstra et al., 2024). Therefore, it is important to sustainably manage soils and protect them from degradation in order to maintain healthy soils and ensure food security for future generations (European Commission 2021a and 2021b). This is reflected in a number of international and European strategies, programmes and initiatives (e.g. UN SDGs, EU Green Deal, EU Soil Strategy, EU Soil Mission, etc.) that outline many ambitious policy goals related to sustainable agriculture, soil management and conservation such as taking measures and actions to protect and restore soils, or setting out a vision for achieving healthy soils by 2050. In order to meet such ambitious targets, there is a need to harmonise soil assessment approaches and to introduce/provide appropriate soil policy instruments to support soil health measures. European Commission has put soil protection in a high position on the EU policy agenda as healthy soils, which provide as many ecosystem services as possible (European Commission 2021b), are important to achieve climate neutrality, zero pollution, sustainable food provision and a resilient environment (Panagos et al., 2024). Therefore, the implementation of policy objectives requires the establishment of evidence-based harmonised assessment criteria and indicators not only for soil threats but also for soil-based ecosystem services.

SERENA Task 4.1 focused on analysing the requirements and assumptions of European and international soil policies and assessing the relevance and applicability to current policies of the indicators selected in the SERENA project for assessing soil threats (ST) and soil-based ecosystem services (SES). For this purpose, a detailed review of a number of international documents (directives, strategies, conventions, initiatives) on soil policy was carried out and, in addition, recommendations from previous projects and reports were analysed. It was checked whether specific soil threats and soil ecosystem services were already addressed by existing policy measures and whether any specific ST/SES indicators necessary for the proper implementation of the goals and objectives of these policies were included (Chapter 3).

In addition, the list of ST/SES indicators proposed in the SERENA project was assessed by stakeholders, who indicated the need to implement wide range of SERENA indicators into national soil policies. Their views on national needs are summarised in Chapter 4. The soil policy analysis carried out allowed the identification of ST/SES indicators needed at different scales (international, EU, national) for the implementation of soil health instruments.

2 Methodology

The objectives of Task 4.1 were implemented in two main phases:

- Phase 1 – desk study on current European and international soil-related policies and initiatives;
- Phase 2 – stakeholder consultation on the list of ST/SES indicators proposed for implementation in the future policy and identification of national needs in this respect.

2.1 Phase 1 – Desk study on current European and international soil-related policies and initiatives

The analysis of the documents (Phase 1) was based on the methodology developed by Jacob et al. (2021) and was carried out in three stages:

- 1) identification/selection of soil related policy documents;

- II) selection of a set of indicators for documents screening; and
 III) analysis of collected documents in the terms of indicators proposed by SERENA.

2.1.1 Identification and selection of soil related policy documents

Several sources of information were analysed to create the list of documents for detailed review in Task T4.1:

- available databases (EUSO; FAO Soil Portal, SoilLEX);
- scientific articles (e.g., Bartkowski et al., 2021; Freluh-Larsen et al., 2017; Panagos et al., 2020; Panagos et al., 2022; Ronchi et al., 2019; Schulte et al., 2019; Vrebos et al., 2017) ;
- report from the European Environmental Agency (Baritz et al., 2021; European Environment Agency, 2023);
- reports from the general EJP SOIL programme (WP2, Jacob et al., 2021 and Pavlů et al., 2021; WP8, Philips et al., 2021; WP6, van Egmond et al., 2021); and
- report from the internal EJP SOIL SIREN project (Faber et al., 2022).

A wide list of 22 documents was prepared (Table 1), and after a first screening of the documents, it was decided to exclude the UNFCCC from further analysis as a very broad framework with limited reference to soil indicators.

Table 1. List of policies/initiatives included in the analysis.

Document
UN Convention to Combat Desertification (UNCCD)
UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC)
UN Sustainable Development Goals (UN SDGS) (SDG 2, SDG 3, SDG 6, SDG 13, SDG 15)
EU Soil strategy for 2030 “Reaping the benefits of healthy soils for people, food, nature and climate”
European Green Deal:
From Farm to Fork Strategy
EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030
European Climate Law
Zero Pollution Action Plan (for Air, Water and Soil)
New Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)
4p1000 Initiative
FAO-ITPS. Protocol for the assessment of Sustainable Soil Management (FAO-ITPS: SSM)
EU Mission “Soil Health and food”
Environmental Liability Directive
Industrial Emissions Directive
EU Forest Strategy
Nitrate Directive
Proposal for a Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience (Soil Monitoring Law)

As the European commission recently published a proposal for a new directive, the so-called Soil Monitoring Law (SML), this document was added to the final list (Table 1).

2.1.2 Selection of a set of indicators for documents screening and links with other SERENA tasks

At this stage, various lists of indicators were analysed for their suitability for use in screening policy documents. The Task 4.1 activity was built on the results of previous EJP Soil SIREN project (Faber et

al., 2022), as well as on the indicators proposed in the EEA report (Baritz et al., 2021; European Environment Agency, 2023) for soil threats characterisation.

In addition, ST/SES indicators from other SERENA Work Packages and tasks were considered in establishing the final list for the analysis of soil policies, i.e. a list of indicators used by SERENA-members to assess ST/SES at national level (Task 3.1, Michel et al., 2022); a list of indicators resulting from the literature review for the prioritisation of threats and ecosystem services in SERENA (Task 2.2, Foldal et al., 2022) and an inventory of definitions and indicators to communicate to stakeholders (Task 1.2, Klimkowicz-Pawlas and Weninger, 2022).

After wide discussion in the Task 4.1 working group, it was decided to adapt the indicators of soil threats and soil ecosystem services proposed in Task 2.2 (Foldal et al., 2022; Foldal and Oorst, 2023) for further analyses of policy documents. Finally, more than 65 indicators were considered (Appendix 1), which characterised 10 STs (soil erosion, soil organic carbon loss, nutrient imbalance, soil acidification, soil contamination, waterlogging, soil sealing, soil compaction, salinization, loss of diversity) and 7 SESs (primary/biomass production, habitat for biodiversity, erosion control, hydrological control, environmental pollution control, GHG and climate regulation/C sequestration, pest and disease control) - Appendix 1.

2.1.3 Analysis of documents in the terms of indicators proposed by SERENA

A comprehensive set of 21 documents (Table 1) relating to soil policy or initiatives at the European and international level was analysed. For this purpose, the Excel questionnaire was developed and distributed to the members of the Task 4.1 working group.

For each document, it was checked whether:

- it addresses soil threats/soil ecosystem services,
- the ST/SES indicators selected in the SERENA project (Appendix 1) are already mentioned in any way (reviewer's yes/no response),
- the proposed indicators are required or not relevant for the correct implementation of the policy in question.

2.2 Phase 2 - Stakeholder assessment of SERENA's ST/SES indicators in the context of national policy needs

Phase 2, i.e. the stakeholder consultation on the list of ST/SES indicators, was implemented in close cooperation with SERENA Work Package 1, Task 1.2, in which a multi-part questionnaire was developed to agree with stakeholders on terminology for key concepts, soil threats and soil ecosystem services (Weninger et al., 2023). In addition, proposed lists of indicators (Appendix 2) for each ST and SES (Foldal and Oorst, 2023; Montagne et al., 2023) were assessed, and one component of this questionnaire was a section relating to national soil policies (Weninger et al., 2023). The survey was conducted between June and September 2023 among a broad and diverse group of stakeholders. A total of 398 participants from 19 countries took part in the survey. For more details on the structure and dissemination of the questionnaire, as well as the results of the stakeholder survey, see Weninger et al. (2023) and Weninger et al. (2024).

As mentioned above, the questionnaire contained two policy questions related to indicators :

1. *'Which ones of the mentioned indicators for this ST/SES are already included in the policy in your country?'*

2. *'Which ones of the mentioned indicators for this ST/SES do you think should be implemented in the soil policy in your country?'*

Under each question, a brief explanation of the term *'soil policy'* was given; *'Soil policy in this context means laws, directives, official assessments, federal soil mapping, etc.'* It was emphasised that regional studies or similar approaches are not included in this assessment (even if conducted by federal institutions).

Each survey participant had two response options: *'yes'* (selection a specific indicator from the list – Appendix 2) and *'no'* (specifying that none from the listed indicators are or should be included in the national policy). Participants unfamiliar with the policy issues could select *'I don't know'*.

3 Phase 1 - Review of international and EU policy documents

A general description of the documents is included in section 3.1, the results of the detailed analysis are given in Appendix 3 and summarised in subsection 3.2. In addition, guidance and recommendations on ST and/or SES indicators from earlier work and the requirements of the new law on soil monitoring and resilience were taken into account (subsection 3.3).

3.1 General overview of the policy documents in terms of indicators proposed by SERENA

3.1.1 UN Convention to Combat Desertification (UNCCD)

The objective of this Convention is to combat desertification and mitigate the effects of drought in countries experiencing serious drought and/or desertification, particularly in Africa, through effective action at all levels, supported by international cooperation and partnership arrangements, in the framework of an integrated approach which is consistent with Agenda 21, with a view to contributing to the achievement of sustainable development in affected areas. Achieving this objective will involve long-term integrated strategies that focus simultaneously, in affected areas, on improved productivity of land, and the rehabilitation, conservation and sustainable management of land and water resources, leading to improved living conditions, in particular at the community level (UNCCD, 2022).

The convention also has the task of defining all the principles and the obligations to be observed in order to implement programmes to combat desertification for the parties. The document provides important details for countries preparing a sub-regional, regional or joint action programme to review progress in combating desertification and harmonise national action programmes. It also serves as a focal point for the promotion and coordination of projects. The act stands as a reference in defining the main key words to describe combating desertification. As described by this convention, some of the keywords analysed are listed:

- *"desertification"* means: land degradation in arid, semi-arid and sub-humid dry areas resulting by various factors, including climatic variations and human activities;
- *"combating desertification"*: activities that are part of integrated land development in arid, semi-arid and sub-humid dry areas for sustainable development that are aimed at: preventing and/or reducing land degradation; rehabilitation of partially degraded land; reclamation of desertified land;
- *"land degradation"* means reduction or loss, in arid, semi-arid and dry sub-humid areas, of the biological or economic productivity and complexity of rainfed cropland, irrigated cropland, or range, pasture, forest and woodlands resulting from land uses or from a process or combination of processes, including processes arising from human activities and habitation patterns,

such as: soil erosion caused by wind and/or water; deterioration of the physical, chemical and biological or economic properties of soil; and long-term loss of natural vegetation;

- “*arid, semi-arid and dry sub-humid areas*” means areas, other than polar and sub-polar regions, in which the ratio of annual precipitation to potential evapotranspiration falls within the range from 0.05 to 0.65.

UNCCD is set within the scope of Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) target 15.3 states: “*By 2030, combat desertification, restore degraded land and soil, including land affected by desertification, drought and floods, and strive to achieve a land degradation-neutral world.*” (UN SDGs, 2024). Being a political international agreement, the convention does not directly address soil-related indicators with a scientific approach. But in a generic way it deals with some indicators such as annual change in degraded or desertified arable land and especially soil erosion by water and wind.

3.1.2 UN Sustainable Development Goals

UN SDGs (UN SDGs, 2024) are a comprehensive framework with many criteria and indicators. The SDGs take the perspective of society: which future development is desirable? Therefore, many criteria present a socio-economic view. The SDGs are not relating directly to soil parameters, but inherently are addressing them. A direct reference to soil parameters is not deemed useful in the SDGs, however several research challenges are directly linked to soil quality and soil management.

SDG 2: Zero Hunger

Focus is on malnutrition and obstacles for even distribution of agricultural produce. The indicators are rather socio-economic parameters. Soil per se is not mentioned, some indicators refer to loss of diversity and biomass production in the context of supplying societies with food and feed. SDG 2 addresses the economic situation on a meta level. Mostly economic metrics are used.

SDG 3: Good Health and Well-Being

SDG 3 addresses societal issues. Although soil health is an integral part of human health and well-being, no interface to soil sciences is established in the description of parameters and indicators of SDG 3 that would refer to soils. The goal has a different focus and does not have a direct relation to soils and does not need to be analyzed in SERENA.

SDG 6: Clean water and sanitation

Clean water is a basic human need, and one that should be easily accessible to all. There is sufficient fresh water on the planet to achieve this. However, due to poor infrastructure, investment and planning, every year millions of people — most of them children and vulnerable groups — die from diseases associated with inadequate water supply, sanitation and hygiene.

SDG 6 exclusively deals with water quality issues. Due to the close link between soil and water the indicators regarding soil contamination strongly related to water quality. Yet, no soil parameter is explicitly addressed in SDG 6.

SDG 13: Climate action

Topic of climate change is addressed from viewpoint of exposure and vulnerability of the society towards climate change. Soil issues are not directly addressed but are part of the topic, *indicators mentioned refer to soil organic carbon loss (SOC stock and SOC concentration), erosion control and GHG emissions* from soils.

SDG 15: Life on Land

SDG 15 aims to “sustainably manage forest, combat desertification, halt and reverse land degradation, and halt biodiversity loss”. Almost all criteria and indicators encompass soil issues. SDG 15 broadly

relates to *soil indicators*: soil erosion (*soil loss by water, wind and tillage erosion*), soil organic carbon loss (*SOC stock and SOC concentration*), soil contamination (*concentration of contaminants, diffuse pollution, locations with potential soil contamination*), soil sealing, salinization (*electrical conductivity, pH*), loss of diversity, biomass production, habitat for biodiversity, erosion control, GHG and climate regulation or C sequestration, pest and disease control.

3.1.3 FAO-ITPS. Protocol for the assessment of Sustainable Soil Management

The objective of this protocol is to provide a framework, based on a set of indicators, for government officials, Non-Government Organizations, and other stakeholders involved in development projects, to determine if implemented soil management practices are sustainable and in line with the definition of Sustainable Soil Management (SSM) included in the Voluntary Guidelines for Sustainable Soil Management (VGSSM) (FAO, 2017; FAO-ITPS, 2020).

The document provides a set of recommended soil indicators that can be monitored to assess Sustainable Soil Management (*soil productivity, soil organic carbon, soil physical properties and soil biological activity*).

In addition, the protocol divides the list of indicators into two groups: one group of recommended indicators, and another group of specific indicators. If soil degradation is caused by specific and identified threats, these should be measured using additional indicators (*soil nutrients, soil erosion, soil salinity, soil biological activity, soil biological diversity, soil pH, available water capacity, soil infiltration rate, soil penetration resistance and soil pollution*) to more specifically assess the impact of implemented management practices. The indicators were chosen as they are widely developed and rely on internationally established and harmonized measurement methods. They are considered as reference indicators for all the additional indicators that might be implemented, as needed, by protocol users. The protocol is not only a reference point for the identification and definition of soil indicators but is a practical guide for planning a Sustainable Soil Management assessment. SSM assessment can determine the effectiveness of changes generated by the implementation of SSM practices and assess the impact of soil management for sustainability in the short, medium and long term.

3.1.4 Recommendations of the EU Mission “Soil Health and Food”

The EU Mission on Soil Health and Food has been launched on 29 September 2021 and ‘A Soil Deal for Europe’ was presented with the mission’s implementation plan (European Commission, 2021a). The relevance of the mission is reflected in its integration in a wide range of EU strategies and policy documents (e.g., Farm to Fork Strategy, Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, Zero Pollution Action Plan for air, water and soil, EU Forest Strategy, EU Soil Strategy for 2030). The Mission emphasizes the fundamental importance of soils, including climate change, sustainable food and biomass production, loss of biodiversity and provision of ecosystem services with contribution also to the European Green Deal targets on sustainable farming, biodiversity, climate resilience and zero-pollution.

‘A Soil Deal for Europe’ sets a target of placing 100 Living labs and lighthouses to lead the transition towards healthy soils by 2030. This is combined with an ambitious transdisciplinary research and innovation programme (e.g., in close coordination with the European Joint Partnership EJP Soil), a harmonized soil monitoring framework (in cooperation with Member States, the JRC, Eurostat, and the EEA) and increased soil literacy and communication to raise people’s awareness. Mission implementation plan describes specifically each aforementioned operational objectives, activities and the use of supported resources. It is considered that Common Agricultural Policy will act in synergy with the mission’s objectives and contribute to its implementation. Also, an outline of how EU and Member State policies and instruments could be mobilised for the soil health mission is analysed.

The implementation plan of the Mission 'A Soil Deal for Europe' has eight specific objectives (European Commission, 2021a):

1. Reduce land degradation relating to desertification
2. Conserve and increase soil organic carbon stocks
3. No net soil sealing and increase the reuse of urban soils
4. Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration
5. Prevent erosion
6. Improve soil structure to enhance habitat quality for soil biota and crops
7. Reduce the EU global footprint on soils
8. Increase soil literacy in society across MS

The Mission (European Commission, 2021a) proposes to use a set of 8 *soil health indicators* to assess current status which will serve as a starting point for further discussion with Member States:

1. *Presence of pollutants, excess nutrients and salts*; When present in higher concentrations than allowed by health regulations or plant requirements: soils are unhealthy. A reduction in levels below recognized threshold values indicates an improvement in soil health.
2. *Soil organic carbon stock*; Organic matter is important for adsorbing nutrients, retaining water and for improving soil structure and workability of soils as well as plant productivity. Soil organic carbon (SOC) is a major constituent (56%) of soil organic matter and the global soil organic carbon reservoir of soils is two to three times bigger than the carbon as atmospheric CO₂. Therefore, an increase in SOC concentration and stock allows drawing down CO₂ from the atmosphere and an improvement in soil health.
3. *Soil structure including soil bulk density and absence of soil sealing and erosion*; Good soil structure as indicated by reduced bulk density, the absence of soil sealing and erosion allows for healthy root growth, reaching all parts of the soil and allowing infiltration of rainwater to prevent runoff and soil loss.
4. *Soil biodiversity*; Presence of functional diversity of appropriate bacteria and fungi and of soil animal communities that are important for soil functions and services, such as soil structure, litter decomposition, organic carbon storage and nutrients cycling promotes all soil functions. Currently, nematodes and earthworms are well tested. Ongoing research will soon deliver indicators for soil microbial parameters.
5. *Soil nutrients and acidity (pH)*; Essential nutrients for plant growth in part at least, derived from soils include N, P, K, S, Ca. A range of plant micro-nutrients usually found at very low concentrations (parts per million) in soils may limit plant growth, such as boron (B), chlorine (Cl), cobalt (Co), copper (Cu), iron (Fe), manganese (Mn), molybdenum (Mo) and zinc (Zn). Soil pH affects many chemical and biological processes, including plant nutrients availability and the balance and functions of soil microbial communities. In farmland and forestry soils, an optimal balance is required for growth. In supporting biodiversity-rich ecosystems, nutrient limitations provide an essential set of sub-optimal conditions to support a diversity of biota above and below-ground.
6. *Vegetation cover*; The annual duration and diversity of the vegetation cover and its net primary productivity is essential for soil health, providing nutrients for soil biodiversity and carbon inputs to soil organic matter, also reducing erosion and surface runoff. A more diverse and long duration cover indicates conditions favourable to soil biodiversity and health and increasing vegetation cover is also valuable for urban settings.
7. *Landscape heterogeneity*; Landscape heterogeneity, including farmland (field size, fragmentation, presence of natural green elements), forestry (types of forest, monocultures, clear-cuts with bare land) and urban green infrastructures (adequate presence). The diversity

of landscape elements (composition) and the way these elements are distributed, including their relative size and their location in relation to the morphology (configuration) strongly influence biodiversity, the water cycle and soil erosion.

8. *Forest cover*; Area of forest and other wooded lands, classified by the number of species, the share of nonnative tree species, and the proportion of natural and artificial regeneration. In forests, soil health is influenced by the naturalness in terms of species composition and the management practices, including disturbance by clear cuts.

In addition to these indicators, it is proposed to track management activities as a proxy for soil health. This is proposed for measuring progress towards soil improvement where health indicators are slow to show changes and soil issues are slow to recover. However, the Mission board highlights the importance of focusing on the longer term on a thorough monitoring of soil health indicators as management practices may not deliver the intended outcomes.

3.1.5 European Green Deal

The two documents "*Decision of the EU parliament and of the council on a General Union Environment Program to 2030*" and "*Communication [...] the European Green Deal*" present the policy ambitions of EU regarding environment (European Commission, 2019). The soils are mentioned as entities to be preserved due to their contribution to ecosystem services, and a law protecting the Soil Health is announced (for 2023). Nevertheless, no indicators of soil threats, or soil quality, or soil-based ecosystem services are mentioned.

3.1.6 From Farm to Fork Strategy

The Farm to Fork Strategy (European Commission, 2020a) is a part of the framework of Green Deal and introduces European Commission objectives and actions on sustainable food production throughout food chain. Soil is not a special focus of the strategy. However, targets for 2030 considering fertilizer and pesticide use and organic farming are as follows:

- reducing nutrient losses by at least 50%, while ensuring that there is no deterioration in soil fertility,
- reducing the use of fertilizers by at least 20%,
- reducing the overall use and risk of chemical pesticides by 50% and the use of more hazardous pesticides by 50%,
- at least 25% of the EU's agricultural land is under organic farming.

The terms '*pesticides*' and '*nutrients (including nitrogen and phosphorus)*' in the strategy are used in general, not addressing any indicators or specifying soils in detail. Soil health and functions have been pointed in the context of Research and Innovation framework programmes.

3.1.7 EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030

The European Green Deal – the EU's growth strategy – will be the compass for our recovery, ensuring that the economy serves people and society and gives back to nature more than it takes away. The business case for biodiversity is compelling. Industry and companies rely on genes, species, and ecosystem services as critical inputs for production, notably for medicines. Over half of global GDP depends on nature and the services it provides, with three key economic sectors – construction, agriculture, and food and drink – all highly dependent on it. Biodiversity conservation has potential direct economic benefits for many sectors of the economy. For example, conserving marine stocks could increase annual profits of the seafood industry by more than €49 billion, while protecting coastal wetlands could save the insurance industry around €50 billion annually through reducing flood damage losses. The overall benefit/cost ratio of an effective global programme for the conservation of remaining wild nature worldwide is estimated to be at least 100 to 14. Natural capital investment,

including restoration of carbon-rich habitats and climate-friendly agriculture, is recognised to be among the five most important fiscal recovery policies, which offer high economic multipliers and positive climate impact. It will be important for the EU to tap into this potential to ensure prosperity, sustainability and resilience in the recovery.

The biodiversity crisis and the climate crisis are intrinsically linked. Climate change accelerates the destruction of the natural world through droughts, flooding and wildfires, while the loss and unsustainable use of nature are in turn key drivers of climate change. But just as the crises are linked, so are the solutions. Nature is a vital ally in the fight against climate change. Nature regulates the climate, and nature-based solutions, such as protecting and restoring wetlands, peatlands and coastal ecosystems, or sustainably managing marine areas, forests, grasslands and agricultural soils, will be essential for emission reduction and climate adaptation. Planting trees and deploying green infrastructure will help us to cool urban areas and mitigate the impact of natural disasters.

The EU Biodiversity Strategy (European Commission, 2020c) raises important issues on indicators. Yet, the focus is on the definition of policy targets. For a specific choice of suitable indicators the Biodiversity Strategy refers to other programmes such as the Common Agricultural Policy. The Biodiversity Strategy addresses biodiversity in its full breadth (richness of biotopes, structural diversity, species communities from plants to animals, to microbes, genetic diversity). It also addresses the problem of invasive species.

No specific soil indicators are addressed. Yet, in the complete coverage of the topic biodiversity, all indicators are indirectly addressed.

3.1.8 European Climate Law

The European Climate Law (European Commission, 2020d) sets a legally binding target of net zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2050. Climate neutrality by 2050 means achieving net zero GHG emissions for EU countries as a whole, mainly by cutting emissions, investing in green technologies and protecting the natural environment. The European Climate Law requests indicators for monitoring the progress and achievements: one is related to the actions on adaptation to climate change (regulation EU 2018/1999), another one is related to the number of Member States with adaptation strategies and plans (regulation EU 2018/1999).

3.1.9 Zero pollution Action Plan (for Air, Water and Soil)

As part of the European Green Deal, the Zero Pollution Action Plan (European Commission, 2021d) sets out a vision for a pollution-free environment and brings together all current and planned efforts in an integrated strategy. This Action Plan recognizes that soil pollution harms human, soil and environmental health and is one of the main reasons for the loss of biodiversity and the ability of ecosystems to provide services such as carbon sequestration. The main objective of this Action Plan is to provide a compass for integrating pollution prevention into all relevant EU policies.

The zero pollution hierarchy includes:

- prevention of pollution at source through clean production and circular economy;
- minimization of releases and exposure;
- elimination of pollution and remediation.

With regard to soils, there is a need for a framework to monitor the state of soils in the EU and to take action at all levels to address soil pollution and degradation. Pesticide pollution (air, water and soil) should be reduced by reducing their overall use and risks, including the most hazardous ones, by 50% by 2030. No specific indicator of soil contamination, but in order to meet the ambitious targets of the zero pollution plan, it is necessary to monitor the content of organic and inorganic contaminants in the soil.

3.1.10 EU Soil strategy for 2030 “Reaping the benefits of healthy soils for people, food, nature and climate”

The EU Soil Strategy for 2030 (European Commission, 2021b) sets out a framework and concrete measures to protect and restore soils, and ensure that they are used sustainably. The strategy is a key deliverable of the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, and will contribute to the objectives of the European Green Deal. The key objective of the EU Soil Strategy is to achieve good soil health by 2050 through fulfilling the medium-term objectives by 2030.

According to the Strategy soils are healthy when they are in good chemical, biological and physical conditions and continuously provide as many of the following ecosystem services as possible:

- provide food and biomass production, including in agriculture and forestry;
- absorb, store and filter water and transform nutrients and substances, thus protecting groundwater bodies;
- provide the basis for life and biodiversity, including habitats, species, and genes;
- act as a carbon reservoir;
- provide a physical platform and cultural services for humans and their activities;
- act as a source of raw materials;
- constitute an archive of geological, geomorphological, and archaeological heritage.

The main objectives of the strategy are:

- protecting organic soils through limiting drainage in order to maintain and increase soil carbon stocks and increasing soil carbon in agricultural land;
- working towards a circular economy (re-use of excavated soil, limiting land take and reducing soil sealing);
- protecting soil biodiversity (monitoring antibiotic resistance genes in agricultural soils);
- promoting sustainable soil management through the Common Agricultural Policy and allowing landowners to test their soils free of charge;
- combating desertification;
- tackling pollution (reducing the use of pesticides, perfluoroalkyl compounds (PFAS), microplastics and antimicrobials);
- restoring degraded land and identifying and remediating contaminated land.

Overall, the Soil Strategy provides a framework that allows the same level of protection for soils as for water, the marine environment and air. The EU Soil Strategy calls for action to gain knowledge on soil data and monitoring of soils. Actions for soil data harmonization entail efforts in identifying and harmonizing soil data, soil indicators, soil mapping and databases across Europe. The ambition is to have healthy soils in the entirety of Europe by 2050. The Soil Strategy announced new Commission legislative initiatives, i.e. Soil Health Law and Nature Restoration Law. Achieving the objectives of the Strategy requires not only the adoption of new legislation on soil health, but also the updating of existing EU law, including the Emissions Directive, the Sewage Sludge Directive, the Environmental Liability Directive, the Pesticides Directive, the REACH Regulation. There is also a need for development and agreement on indicators of good soil health and for the defining common ranges or thresholds beyond which soils cannot be considered healthy anymore.

3.1.11 New Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)

The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) is a key EU land management policy and a central driver for management of agricultural land. On 2 December, 2021, the agreement on reform of the common agricultural policy was formally adopted. The new legislation, CAP 2023-2027 (European Commission, 2023a), paves the way for a fairer, greener and more performance-based CAP. It will seek to ensure a sustainable future for European farmers, provide more targeted support to smaller farms, and allow

greater flexibility for EU countries to adapt measures to local conditions. Agriculture and rural areas are central to the European Green Deal (European Commission, 2019), and the new CAP will be a key tool in reaching the ambitions of the Farm to Fork (European Commission, 2020a) and biodiversity (European Commission, 2020c) strategies.

Several soil threats and ecosystem services are addressed in various objectives of new CAP:

- Soil erosion, nutrient imbalance and waterlogging are present in the Objective 5 about Natural Resources [indicators: the % of agricultural area at risk of soil erosion (JRC, Impact indicator I.13); Gross nutrient balance in agricultural land and Nitrates in groundwater (EEA, Impact indicators I.11); and Water abstraction in agriculture (Eurostat, Impact indicators I.10, C.20), respectively].
- Soil contamination is present in the Objective 9 about Food and Health Quality [indicator: Risks and impact of pesticides (DG SANTE); Sales of plant protection products (Eurostat); Farming intensity (DG AGRI, FADN) and Area under organic farming (Eurostat)].
- Biodiversity (in general) is included in the Objective 6 about Biodiversity and Ecosystem services [indicators: Farmland Bird Index (EBCC-PECBMS, Impact Indicator I.08); Conservation status of agricultural habitats (EEA-DG ENV, Context indicator C.36); Average number of linear elements (JRC) and Area under NATURA 2000 (NATURA 2000 Barometer, Context indicator C.34)].
- Biomass production is present in the Objectives 1 and 2 about Farm income and competitiveness [indicator: Total Factor Productivity (EBCC-PECBMS, Impact Indicator I.08)].

Some soil threats are not present in the CAP objectives, however could be included to the Objective 5 about Natural Resources (acidification, soil compaction, salinization) or to the Objective 6 about biodiversity and Ecosystem services (soil sealing).

Pest and disease control is not reported explicitly in the new CAP.

3.1.12 EU Action Plan for the Circular Economy

The EU Action Plan for the Circular Economy (European Commission, 2020b) was published by the European Commission in March 2020. This Plan is related to SERENA in its philosophy, emphasizing the co-creation with economic actors, consumers, citizens and civil society organisations. The circular economy will make a decisive contribution to achieving climate neutrality by 2050, and decoupling economic growth from resource use. But only mentions the soil in page 11: "*promoting initiatives to reduce soil sealing, rehabilitate abandoned or contaminated brownfields and increase the safe, sustainable and circular use of excavated soils*". On the other side, the threats related to Environmental pollution control and GHG emissions are included.

3.1.13 4p1000 Initiative

The International "*4 per 1000*" Initiative was launched by France on 1 December 2015, at COP 21. Their objectives are perfectly related to those of SERENA, particularly in its vision of involving stakeholders (bottom-up and top-down approaches). *4per1000* wants to involve stakeholders to develop a global monitoring platform to quantify soil carbon stocks, and to design public policies encouraging farmers to adopt soil friendly agricultural practices. It proposes a transition towards a regenerative, productive and highly resilient agriculture, based on adequate land and soil management. This initiative is focusses on the Carbon market. It is notorious that, in the list of Farmers and Foresters Organisations who collaborate in *4p1000*, there are no farmers or foresters from Spain (which is the fourth largest agricultural producer in the European Union); it would be interesting to know what is the means of dissemination of this Initiative among European farmers.

3.1.14 Environmental Liability Directive

This EU Directive (2003-2006-2009-2013) is dedicated to the prevention and remediation of environmental damage (EU, 2004). Polluted soils are concerned, not specifically agricultural soils. The Directive provide elements to prevent and remedy environmental damage based in the "polluter-pays" principle. No indicator is provided (neither for air, soil or water).

3.1.15 Industrial Emissions Directive

The Emission Industrial EU Directive (EU, 2010) establishes a general framework for the control of the main industrial activities in order to prevent, reduce and as far as possible eliminate pollution from industrial activities in compliance with the "polluter pays" principle and the principle of pollution prevention. This Directive includes the following definition of "soil" - *"the top layer of the Earth's crust situated between the bedrock and the surface. The soil is composed of mineral particles, organic matter, water, air and living organisms"*. The Directive includes a list of polluting substances for air and water, but do not provide indicators for soils. In order to assess the state of soil contamination, a baseline report is required before the start of the installation operation, and periodic monitoring (every 10 years) is required in relation to harmful substances to be used, produced or released by the installation concerned.

3.1.16 EU Forest Strategy

The new EU Forest Strategy (European Commission, 2021c) aims to unlock the potential of forests for our future, in full respect for the principle of subsidiarity, best available scientific evidence and Better Regulation requirements. It is anchored in the European Green Deal and the EU 2030 Biodiversity Strategy and it recognises the central and multi-functional role of forests, and the contribution of foresters and the entire forest-based value chain for achieving by 2050 a sustainable and climate-neutral economy while ensuring that all of ecosystems are restored, resilient, and adequately protected.

The EU Forest Strategy relies on many indicators that have been developed over the years by Forest Europe (<https://foresteurope.org/>). These criteria and indicators are addressing forest health, forest ecology, and forest economy. A reference to forest soils is rarely made and is not addressing specific parameters. The Forest Strategy reaches out to the Biodiversity Strategy. The Strategy declares that eventually required new criteria and indicators will be negotiated by expert groups.

The EU Forest Strategy addresses the main topics on a meta-level. The document refers to CAP and rather non-specifically to indicators that are instrumental in other activities (e.g. European Forest Fire Information System EFFIS). Monitoring of (yet) unspecified parameters is recommended.

3.1.17 Nitrate Directive

The Nitrate Directive (EU, 1991) is a rather old European document (initial version in 1991, amended in 2003 and 2008). The objective is to propose measures to limit water nitrate pollution from agricultural sources. It concerns then only the "contamination" soil threat in SERENA, and does not give any elements related to soils, but only recommendations about the livestock manures which are allowed to be spread over agricultural soils within one year.

3.2 Indicators found in European and international soil policy documents

The analysis carried out (section 3.1, Appendix 3) shows that several documents (UN SDG3, EU Green Deal, Zero Pollution Action Plan, Environmental Liability Directive, Industrial Emission Directive, Nitrate Directive) do not include any specific soil indicators. However, it is worth highlighting that for the proper implementation policies related to the pollution prevention and control (to which aforementioned Zero Pollution Action Plan, Environmental Liability Directive, Industrial Emission

Directive refer) it is necessary to monitor the content of organic and inorganic contaminants in the soil. Soil contamination indicators are therefore required.

Only in seven documents more than 10 indicators are mentioned, most in: UN SDG 15, FAO-ITPS: SSM, Forest Strategy, EU Mission, Biodiversity Strategy and Soil Strategy (Figure 1).

Figure 1: The number of indicators found in the analysed document.

However, in many documents, the indicators are mentioned in very general terms (as a general threat rather than a specific indicator), e.g. *soil erosion* (UNCCD, FAO-ITPS: SSM, EU Mission “Soil Health and food”, Biodiversity Strategy, New CAP), *nutrient imbalance* (new CAP, Soil Strategy), *soil sealing* (EU Mission “Soil Health and food”, Biodiversity Strategy, Soil Strategy), *salinization* (UNCCD), *loss of diversity* (UNCCD, Biodiversity Strategy, Soil Strategy, new CAP, Forest Strategy), *soil contamination* (UNCCD, FAO-ITPS: SSM, EU Mission “Soil Health and food”, Soil Strategy, new CAP). These documents do not define specific indicators, but rather present a concept, assumptions or ambitious goals for which appropriate indicators of soil threats or soil ecosystem services are required.

In general, strategies (e.g. Biodiversity, Soil or Forest strategy) establish a certain conceptual framework and usually tend to expect an appropriate set of indicators will be negotiated/developed through additional projects or funding schemes.

Most of the indicators proposed in SERENA (Appendix 1; Foldal et al., 2022) appeared in less than 5 documents analysed, with indicators such as *potential nutrients*, *available nutrients*, *micronutrients*, *waterlogging*, *soil porosity*, *soil penetration resistance* mentioned only once (Appendix 3). Only a short list of analysed indicators (Table 2) is mentioned in 6 – 10 documents. The policy goals, objectives and requirements most often referred to 3 soil threats (SOC loss, soil erosion and loss of diversity) and 4 ecosystem services (GHG and climate regulation, environmental pollution control, habitat for biodiversity and erosion control) – Table 2. This finding is in line with the results of SERENA 2.2 Task (Foldal and Oorst, 2023), which prioritised ST/SES and showed that soil organic carbon loss and soil erosion were very important, while loss of diversity was important for Member States.

Table 2. The most frequently mentioned indicators (in > 25% documents)

ST/SEs	indicator	number of documents	Examples of documents
Soil threats			
SOC loss	SOC stock	9	SDG13, SDG 15, FAO-ITPS: SSM, EU Mission, Biodiv. Strat., Soil Strat., Forest Strat.
	SOC concentration	7	SDG13, SDG 15, FAO-ITPS: SSM, EU Mission, Biodiv. Strat., Soil Strat., Forest Strat.
Soil erosion	Soil loss by wind/water erosion	6	UNCCD, SDG 15, FAO-ITPS: SSM, EU Mission, Biodiv. Strat., Forest Strat.
Loss of diversity	Density of earthworms occurrence	6	SDG2, SDG15, FAO-ITPS: SSM, EU Mission, Biodiv. Strat., Soil Strat., Forest Strat.
	Biodiversity indices	6	SDG2, SDG15, FAO-ITPS: SSM, Forest Strat.
	Microbial biomass values	6	SDG2, SDG15, FAO-ITPS: SSM, EU Mission, Forest Strat.
Soil based ecosystem services			
Environmental pollution control	Concentration of pollutants	8	SDG15, FAO-ITPS: SSM, EU Mission, Farm2Fork, Biodiv. Strat., Soil Strat.,
GHG and climate regulation/C sequestration	GHG emissions	10	SDG13, SDG15, FAO-ITPS: SSM, EU Mission, Farm2Fork, EU Climate Law, Soil Strat., Forest Strat.
	Potential C sequestration	7	SDG15, FAO-ITPS: SSM, EU Mission, Farm2Fork, Biodiv. Strat., EU Climate Law, Forest Strat.
Habitat for biodiversity	Diversity/richness	6	SDG15, FAO-ITPS: SSM, EU Mission, Soil Strat., Forest Strat.
Erosion control	Soil erosion rates	6	SDG13, SDG15, FAO-ITPS: SSM, EU Mission, Biodiv. Strat., Forest Strat.

It can be stated that the most important for the international policy implementation are *SOC stock* and *SOC concentration* required (or included) in 9 and 7 documents, respectively (Table 2). In addition, important indicators are: *soil loss by wind/water erosion*, *earthworms occurrence*, *biodiversity indices* and *microbial biomass*; all mentioned in 6 various documents. Regarding soil ecosystem services, the most frequently mentioned are: *concentration of pollutants*, *GHG emissions*, *potential C sequestration*, *diversity/richness* and *soil erosion rates* (Table 2). Similar ecosystem services (e.g. GHG and climate regulation) were also identified as priorities at the national level (Foldal and Oorst, 2023).

3.3 Indicators in the recommendations of previous work and the requirements of the Soil Monitoring Law

3.3.1 SIREN recommendations

The internal EJP SOIL SIREN project reviewed national approaches to the use of soil data in the assessment of soil ecosystem services (Faber et al., 2022). Based on literature, international policy, feedback from international stakeholders, extensive use in national soil monitoring and EU projects on agricultural soil quality assessment, a synthesis of policy-relevant soil quality indicators (*'minimum data set'*) possible for use in harmonised soil monitoring in Europe was developed (Table 3). Faber et al. (2022) showed that different indicators are used in different Member States, with soil organic carbon content and soil organic C stock being assessed most frequently. In contrast, indicators for

water regulation and persistent organic pollutants are rarely implemented and no biological indicators are included. Therefore, there is a need to implement them in harmonised pan-European monitoring.

Table 3. Indicators ('minimum data set') suggested for use at Tier 1 (Faber et al. 2022).

Policy indicators	Soil Quality Indicator
Soil physical condition	Texture
	Porosity
	Bulk density
Soil fertility	C concentration
	Total N
	P
	K
	pH
Erosion evaluation	Based on calculation
Salinity	Electric conductivity
Contamination	Heavy metal trace elements
Other contaminants	Recommended to be included
Soil biodiversity	
Water regulation	

3.3.2 MINOTAUR recommendations

The main objective of another internal EJP SOIL project MINOTAUR is to analyse different aspects of soil biodiversity and provide models, maps and policy-relevant indicators with validated reference values for monitoring soil biodiversity and related functions.

Table 4. Preliminary recommendations from the MINOTAUR project¹ for 'Loss of soil biodiversity'.

Level of assessment	Recommendation
<u>Tier I group:</u>	<p><i>Functional diversity:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - soil basal respiration - microbial biomass; - enzyme activity (fluorogenic substrates); <p><i>Structural diversity:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - metabarcoding of microorganisms (bacteria, fungi); - abundance, diversity and ecological indices of nematodes; - abundance, diversity and ecological indices of microarthropods; - abundance, diversity and ecological indices of earthworms;
<u>Tier II group</u> optional soil descriptors for biodiversity:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - specific groups and functional genes (qPCR) - soil metagenomics for biomarkers of soil health - microbial necromass - Soil fauna activity (i.e. organic matter degradation) - N mineralization - ecophysiological profile (AWCD) - invasive alien species and plant pests

¹/Source: https://ejpsoil.eu/fileadmin/projects/ejpsoil/WP8/Soil_monitoring/2023-11-03_EJP_SOIL_Feedback_to_Soil_Monitoring_Law_MINOTAUR_Biological_Indicators.pdf

As a first result of the project, preliminary recommendations (Table 4) to the proposed Soil Monitoring Law directive were published in the document '*Feedback to the Soil Monitoring Law from the EJP SOIL internal project 'MINOTAUR' on soil biological indicators*'. It has been pointed out that the basal soil

respiration contained in the proposed Soil Monitoring Law (European Commission, 2023b) is insufficient to assess soil biodiversity and that indicators including both functional and structural soil biodiversity should be considered to accurately assess this threat (Table 4).

3.3.3 European Environmental Agency report

The EEA report (European Environment Agency, 2023) provides: an overview of information on the main soil threats such as soil organic carbon loss, soil nutrients loss (N, P), soil acidification, soil pollution, soil biodiversity loss, soil erosion, soil compaction and soil sealing, and in-depth discussion of the indicators used to assess these threats. Twelve key soil quality indicators (Table 5) were selected for their relevance to assessing soil degradation (unhealthy soils) associated with various important soil functions or ecosystem services. It was assessed that in most cases the selected indicators are well established, the availability of data is acceptable at the European level and they are appropriate to describe key types of soil degradation and impairment of key soil services.

Table 5. Indicators and thresholds recommended in the EEA report (2023) for agricultural land.

Soil threat	Indicator	Thresholds	Comment
Soil organic carbon loss	Falling below optimal SOC	Light soils: <1.2% SOC Medium soils: 1.2-1.9% SOC Heavy soils: >1.9% SOC	SOC: clay ratio optimum SOC content as 10% of the clay content/vulnerability limit
Nutrient loss	Exceedance of critical levels of Nmin	NH ₃ in air: 1-3 mg NH ₃ m ⁻³ NO ₃ in ground water: 50 mg NO ₃ L ⁻¹ N in surface water: 1.0-2.5 mg N L ⁻¹	Mineral N: sum of available NH ₄ and NO ₃
	Falling below of optimal P	P concentration 25-35 mg/kg (optimal P fertility class)	Extractable P concentration < optimum (value range refers to Mehlich 3-ICP; also available P-Bray P1 and Olsen P)
Soil acidification	Exceedance of critical pH levels	1.pH < 4.5 – 4.7 (critical) 2.pH <5.0-5.5 (avoid)	1. Risk of Al toxicity 2. Limited availability of Ca, Mg, K and P
Soil pollution	Exceedance of screening values for critical risk from heavy metal and organic pollutants	Updated values for Cd, Cu, Pb and Zn (mg/kg): By country Database developed (Cd, Cu, Pb, Zn, As, Hg, Ni, Cr) Organic pollutants	Country-specific values vary broadly and are not necessarily comparable Stratification by land use and soil texture
Soil erosion	Exceedance of actual rate of soil loss by water erosion	2t/ha/year for shallow soils (<70cm depth) 4t/ha/year for deeper soils (≥70cm) (soil loss tolerance)	Soil formation rate: 0.3-1.4 t/ha/year Preliminary thresholds, derivation of site-adapted tolerable soil loss rates recommended The current indicator description includes only soil erosion by water, whereas the threshold addresses all other erosion types
Soil biodiversity loss	Loss of soil biodiversity (subindicators)	To be developed: Exceedance of safe minimum standards of ecosystem conservation	Requires sub-indicators by species and/ or (functional) group

		Exceedance of operating ranges (OR) for specific soil animals and microorganisms	
Soil compaction	Harmful subsoil compaction (subindicators)	Priority (sub)-indicators: Saturated hydraulic conductivity (Ks) <10cm/day Air capacity (AC) <5%	Exceedance of 'action values' Secondary sub-indicators with available thresholds: bulk density, internal soil strength, air permeability and oxygen diffusion
Soil sealing	Sealed area per total land area	national targets to achieve 'No Net Land Take'	

The report shows that existing systems for assessing soil degradation in Europe are not easily comparable and require harmonisation and additional research in this area. It is noted that the development of suitable and widely applicable indicators and threshold values is hampered by the wide diversity of soils, biota and climate in Europe, as well as the diverse political, economic and social conditions determining priorities in this field. It is therefore recommended that the definitions of indicators, methods of analysis and sampling and threshold values should be harmonized and agreed at the level of individual EU countries.

3.3.4 EUSO Dashboard

European Soil Observatory (EUSO) has recently developed the Soil Health Dashboard that provides the first comprehensive pan-EU assessment of soil degradation (mainly soil threats) based on the latest state-of-the-art indicators of soil degradation. EUSO Dashboard includes 19 indicators with proposed thresholds (Table 6) and is still being updated (Panagos et al., 2024).

Table 6. Soil degradation processes, indicators and thresholds included in the EUSO Health Dashboard (Panagos et al., 2024)

Soil degradation	Indicator	Threshold
Soil erosion	Water erosion	Erosion rate > 2 t/ha/year
	Wind erosion	
	Tillage erosion	
	Harvest erosion	
	Post-fire recovery	Recovery rate < 1
Soil pollution	Copper excess	Cu concentration > 100 mg/kg
	Mercury excess	Hg concentration > 0.5 mg/kg
	Zinc excess	Zn concentration > 100 mg/kg
	Cadmium excess	Cd concentration > 1mg/kg
	Arsenic excess	Probability of high As (> 45 mg/kg) > 5%
Soil nutrients	Nitrogen surplus	Agricultural area where N surplus > 50 mg/kg
	Phosphorus deficiency	P deficiency < 20 mg/kg
	Phosphorus excess	P excess > 50 mg/kg
Loss of SOC	Distance to maximum SOC level	Distance from 'maximum' SOC >60%
Loss of soil biodiversity	Potential threat to biological functions	≥ Moderately high level of risk
Soil compaction	Soil packing density	High packing density (>1.75 g/cm ³)
Salinisation	Secondary salinisation	Areas in Mediterranean biogeographical region where >30% is equipped for irrigation
Loss of organic soils	Peatland degradation	Peatlands under hotspots of cropland
Soil sealing	Built-up areas	No threshold applied (all built-up areas)

3.3.5 Soil Monitoring Law

The Proposal for a Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience (i.e. Soil Monitoring Law) was initially published on 5 July 2023 (European Commission, 2023b) with the aim of protecting, restoring and ensuring the sustainable use of all soils in Europe. In June 2024, the Council approved the text of the overall approach to the Soil Monitoring (European Commission, 2024). Trilogue discussions are still ongoing to clarify the directive and agree on a final version of the document. This document addresses all major soil threats, i.e. loss of soil organic carbon, erosion, salinization, compaction, nutrients imbalance, contamination, sealing, acidification and loss of soil biodiversity. The ‘Soil Monitoring and Resilience’ directive provides a framework for:

- monitoring and assessment of soil health;
- sustainable soil management;
- and management of contaminated sites.

The proposal for the Directive defines a number of terms (including 'soil health') and establishes soil units and districts. To assess soil health in relation to specific threats, a set of indicators (Table 7) and, for some of them, soil health criteria have been proposed.

Table 7. Soil indicators proposed in the Soil Monitoring Law (European Commission, 2024)

Aspect of soil degradation	Soil descriptor	Criteria for healthy soil condition	
Part A: soil descriptors with criteria established at Union level			
Salinisation	Electrical Conductivity (deci-Siemens per meter)	< 4 dS m ⁻¹ when using saturated soil paste extract (eEC) measurement method, or equivalent criterion if using another measurement method	
Loss of soil organic carbon	Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) concentration (g per kg) evaluated as a ratio SOC to Clay content	For mineral soils: SOC/Clay ratio > 1/13 (that is SOC content to the content of clay fraction (fraction <0.002 mm))	
Subsoil compaction	Bulk density in subsoil (g per cm ³)	Soil texture	range
		sand, loamy sand, sandy loam, loam	<1.80
Sandy clay loam, loam, clay loam, silt, silt loam		<1.75	
silt loam, silty clay loam		<1.65	
Sandy clay, silty clay, clay loam with 35-45% clay		<1.58	
Clay		<1.47	
	Optional: -Saturated hydraulic conductivity – Ksat (cm/day) -Air capacity (%)	≥ 10 cm/day ≥ 5%	
Part B: soil descriptors with criteria established at Member States level			
Excess nutrient content in soil	Extractable phosphorus (mg per kg)	< “maximum value”; MS shall define their own ‘maximum value’	

Soil erosion	Soil erosion rate (t/ha/y)	< “maximum value”; MS shall define their own ‘maximum value’
Soil contamination	Concentration of heavy metals in soil: As, Sb, Cd, Co, Cr (total), Cu, Hg, Pb, Ni, Tl, V, Zn (mg per kg) Concentration of a selection of organic contaminants	Reasonable assurance, obtained from soil point sampling, identification and investigation of contaminated sites and any other relevant information, that no unacceptable risk for human health and the environment from soil contamination exists. Natural and anthropogenic background levels should be taken into account in the risk assessment.
Reduction of soil water retention and infiltration	Water retention: -Soil water holding capacity of the soil sample (% of water/total soil (volume or mass) Water infiltration: -Saturated hydraulic conductivity – Ksat (cm/day) -Air capacity (%)	The estimated value for the total water holding capacity, the saturated hydraulic conductivity and the air capacity of a soil unit is above the minimal threshold and may also addressed by river basin or subbasin, taking into account water processes occurring at that scale.
Loss of soil organic carbon	Soil organic carbon stocks (tC/ha) Optional: Soil organic carbon content (g/kg)	Contribute to national targets for net greenhouse gas removals in the LULUCF sector. >‘maximum value’ The ‘maximum values’ shall be laid down by the MS by soil texture.
Part C: Soil descriptors without criteria		
Excess nutrient content in soil	Total nitrogen in soil (mg g ⁻¹) SOC to N ratio	
Acidification	Soil acidity (pH) Optional descriptor: Base saturation (i.e (Ca+Mg+K)/effective CEC)	
Topsoil compaction	Bulk density in topsoil (A-horizon) (g cm ⁻³) Optional: -Saturated hydraulic conductivity – Ksat (cm/day) -Air capacity (%)	
Loss of soil biodiversity	MS shall select at least one soil descriptor for biodiversity such as but not limited to: - metabarcoding of bacteria, fungi, protists and animals; - phospholipid fatty acid analysis (PFLA); - abundance and diversity of nematodes; - abundance and diversity of earthworms (in cropland); - abundance and diversity of springtails; - abundance and diversity of native ants; - bacterial diversity based on DNA; - soil biological quality based on arthropods (QBS-ar); - presence of invasive alien species and plant pests.	

Optional: Loss of biological activity	MS may select soil descriptors for biological activity such as but not limited to: -soil basal respiration ((mm ³ O ₂ g ⁻¹ hr ⁻¹) in dry soil; -microbial biomass; -soil respiration; -enzyme activity.
Part D: Soil sealing and soil destruction indicators	
Soil sealing and soil destruction	Total sealed soils and destroyed soils (km ² and % of MS surface) Soil sealing and soil destruction, de-sealing, net-sealing (average per year – in km ² and % of MS surface) Total settlement area (km ² and % of MS surface) Land use change towards and from settlement area (average per year – in km ² and % of MS surface) Optional indicators: -soil artificialisation -land fragmentation -land recycling rate -land taken for commercial activities, logistic hubs, renewable energies, surfaces such as airports, roads, mines -consequences of soil sealing and soil destruction such as quantification of loss of ecosystem services, change in floods intensity No criteria

From the analysis of other projects' recommendations on indicators (subchapters 3.3.1 – 3.3.4), it appears that they are linked to soil quality indicators (e.g. SIREN) and that they mainly take into account soil threats. Also, the proposal for a new Directive related to soil health (SML) only considers soil degradation (i.e. threats to soil, chapter 3.3.5) with only a general reference to soil ecosystem services.

4 Phase 2 – National policy needs for ST and SES indicators based on stakeholders evaluation

At this stage, we asked stakeholders whether any of the indicators proposed in the SERENA project (Appendix 2) for assessing ST/SESs are included in official national legislation, directives or assessments, and whether respondents thought it was necessary to include any indicators in national policies. The questionnaire was distributed to a wide range of participants from 27 EU countries (Weninger et al., 2023 and 2024).

A total of 398 participants from 19 countries took part in the survey, with the majority - two thirds - of the responses coming from four countries, i.e. France, Spain, Austria and Germany (Weninger et al., 2024).

4.1 SERENA indicators included in the national policy

At the beginning we intended to check whether the ST/SES indicators proposed in SERENA (Appendix 2) are already taken into account in national policies in EU member states. A summary of the responses to the first policy question "*Which ones of the mentioned indicators for this ST/SES are already included in the policy in your country?*" is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Response of stakeholders (in %) to the question 'which indicators of ST/SES are already included in national policy'. Numbers in brackets on left indicate sample size (i.e. number of valid responses for the respective ST/SES).

The majority of respondents (75% on average) answered in the negative, indicating that none of the proposed indicators are considered in their country's policies or that they have no knowledge of them (Figure 2). The number of negative responses was lowest (37%) for the very well-recognised and widely described threat *soil contamination* and highest (94%) for the term *waterlogging*. This was probably due to the structure of the participants in the study, with the majority of stakeholder (70%) being academics and researchers, and advisors and policy makers comprised only 9.5% and 2.7% respectively (Weninger et al., 2024). Moreover, this can be linked to the long history of *soil contamination* research dating back to the 1970s, when work began on limiting the level of soil contamination and legislation began to be implemented in this area. The high number of negative responses in the case of *waterlogging* may be due to a misunderstanding of the meaning of the term itself, which was also reflected in the opinions on definitions, the lowest score given to *waterlogging* (Weninger et al., 2024).

Stakeholders for only one SES and three STs identified specific indicators that were already included in national policy; these were: 'concentrations of various/common contaminants' for *soil contamination*

and *pollution control*, 'certain thresholds, limits or target values' for *nutrient imbalance* and 'pH value' for *soil acidification*. Which indicates that the implementation of recent soil policies, e.g. SML, can be a major challenge at national level.

4.2 Stakeholders' opinion on national policy needs for ST/SES indicators

The structure of answers to the second question of the survey "Which ones of the mentioned indicators for this ST/SES do you think should be implemented in the soil policy in your country?" is different. In this case, the majority of stakeholders gave a positive response, with an average of 70% of all respondents believing that national policy should take into account indicators of both all soil ecosystem services (59-75% positive responses) and all soil threats (56-82% responses) - Figure 3.

Figure 3: Response of stakeholders (in %) to the question 'which indicators of ST/SES should be implemented in national policy'. Numbers in brackets on left indicate sample size (i.e. number of valid responses for the respective ST/SES).

The different indicators received different numbers of responses, depending on the soil threat or ecosystem service (Tables 8 and 9). According to almost half of the respondents (>45%), the several indicators proposed in the SERENA project should be included in national policies.

When analysing the ST indicators (Table 8), respondents most often indicated the need for implementation:

- 'total soil loss' for *soil erosion* (54%),
- 'SOC stock' and 'SOC stock change' for *SOC loss* (53 and 60%, respectively),
- 'thresholds or target values' for *nutrient imbalance* (64%),
- 'pH-value' for soil acidification (67%),
- 'concentration of contaminants' for *soil contamination* (74%),
- 'frequency of soil moisture excess' for *waterlogging* (74%),
- 'penetration resistance' for *soil compaction* (48%),
- 'electrical conductivity' for *soil salinization* (54%) and
- 'soil moisture index' for *soil drought* (58%).

For *soil sealing* and *loss of diversity*, respondents equally scored 3 ('degree of soil sealing', 'change in degree of soil sealing' and 'land take') and 2 ('invertebrate richness' and 'microbial biomass') indicators respectively (Table 8).

Table 8. SERENA indicators of STs with the highest rate (>40%) of stakeholders' responses.

ST	Indicator	Rate of response (%)
Soil erosion	Actual soil loss by water (t/ha/yr)	40
	Total (water, wind, tillage harvesting) soil loss (t/ha/yr)	54
SOC loss	SOC content/concentration (g/kg)	45
	SOC stock (kgC/ha)	53
	SOC stock change (kgC/ha/yr)	60
Nutrient imbalance	Certain thresholds, limits or target values	64
Acidification	pH-value	67
	base cations in soil sorption complex	45
	base saturation	45
Soil contamination	Concentration of common contaminants	74
Waterlogging	frequency or number of days of occurrence of soil moisture excess	74
Soil compaction	Degree of compaction (Ratio of current bulk density to reference bulk density)	39
	Change in bulk density (kg/m ³ /yr)	39
	Penetration resistance (MPa)	48
Soil sealing	Degree of soil sealing (Percentage of sealed soils in a particular area)	52
	Change in the degree of soil sealing (percent per year)	53
	Degree of imperviousness (Percentage of impervious soils in a particular area)	43
	Change in the degree of imperviousness (percent per year)	43
	Land take (Change in land use from natural, semi-natural, forest or agricultural areas to artificial surfaces)	52
Salinization	Electrical conductivity of saturation extract	54
	Sodium adsorption ratio	41
Loss of diversity	Soil invertebrate richness (number of species)	46
	soil microbial biomass (mg C / kg soil) and functional groups	45
	microbial diversity (number of genes / ng of soil DNA)	41
	Earthworm abundance (number of individuals / m ²)	43
Soil drought	Standard precipitation (-evapotranspiration) index	44
	Soil moisture index	58

It is worth emphasising that ‘SOC stock change’, ‘total soil loss’ and ‘change in degree of soil sealing’ have been identified by SERENA as the so-called ideal indicators (Montagne et al., 2023), i.e. the best indicators from a scientific point of view to describe *soil organic carbon loss*, *soil erosion* and *soil sealing* respectively.

On the other hand, with regard to SES (Table 9), the most frequently indicated were:

- ‘potential net PP’ for *primary production* (43%),
- ‘microbial biomass’ and ‘biodiversity’ for *habitat for biodiversity* (46 and 47%, respectively),
- ‘water retention characteristics’ for *hydrological control* (60%),
- ‘diversity/richness’ for *pest control* (58%).

For the other two ecosystem services, 2 indicators each were identified, i.e. ‘concentration of contaminants’ and ‘SOC’ for *pollution control*, and ‘SOC budget’ and ‘changes in SOC stocks’ for *climate regulation*.

Table 9. SERENA indicators of SESs with the highest rate (>40%) of stakeholders’ responses.

SES	Indicator	Rate of response (%)
Primary production	Potential NPP	43
	(total) Plant biomass	41
Habitat for biodiversity	Microbial biomass (mg kg ⁻¹)	46
	Diversity (number of taxa)	47
	SOC content/concentration (g kg ⁻¹)	44
Erosion control	Decrease of erosion risk by vegetation (dimensionless)	34
Hydrological control	Infiltration capacity	47
	Water retention characteristics (available water capacity, field capacity)	60
Pollution control	Concentration of various soil contaminants	52
	Quantity and quality of soil organic carbon	53
	Soil pH	46
	Clay mineral content	40
	Activity of soil microorganisms	46
Climate regulation	Soil organic carbon budget (tC ha ⁻¹ a ⁻¹)	41
	Changes in soil organic carbon stocks (tC ha ⁻¹ a ⁻¹)	42
Pest control	Diversity/richness	59

It is worth noting, that the highest response rate for each ST (Table 8) and SES (Table 9) was given to the indicators rated by stakeholders as the most appropriate to describe ST/SES (Weninger et al., 2024). However, it should be remembered that in the stakeholder group structure, the majority were scientists (70%) with not much participation from farmers, advisors or policy makers. Hence, scientifically sound indicators meeting the criteria of fitness-for-use, sensitivity and interpretability (Montagne et al., 2023) were often indicated. From the perspective of policy makers, which are pragmatic, ST/SES indicators should be simple, easy to implement and low-cost. Another limitation of the survey is that the majority of stakeholder responses, almost 66%, came from only four Member States, i.e. France, Spain, Austria and Germany, despite very wide dissemination (Weninger et al., 2024).

5 Conclusions and recommendations

This deliverable report summarises a detailed analysis of a set of European and international policy documents in terms of the indicators proposed in the SERENA project; stakeholders opinions on the national policy needs in this regard and relevance of ST/SES SERENA indicators for soil policy implementation.

It was found that ST/SES indicators are mentioned very generally in most **EU and international** documents, but the following indicators are required to properly implement many of the soil policy objectives formulated in these documents:

- SOC stock, SOC concentration, soil loss by wind/water erosion, earthworms occurrence, biodiversity indices, microbial biomass (characterizing soil ST);
- concentration of pollutants, GHG emissions, potential C sequestration, diversity/richness and soil erosion rates (characterizing SESs).

Based on stakeholder opinion, the following SERENA indicators can be recommended for implementation at **national level**:

- ST indicators: total soil loss, SOC stock change, thresholds or target values, pH-value, concentration of contaminants, frequency of soil moisture excess, penetration resistance, electrical conductivity, soil moisture index, degree of soil sealing, change in degree of soil sealing, land take, invertebrate richness and microbial biomass.
- SES indicators: potential net PP, biodiversity, water retention characteristics, diversity/richness, concentration of contaminants, quality and quantity of SOC, SOC budget and changes in SOC stocks.

Some indicators of soil threats (e.g. soil erosion rate, SOC concentration and SOC stock, pH-value, concentration of contaminants, electrical conductivity) are already included in the proposal of SML directive on soil monitoring and resilience.

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Appendix 1. Indicators considered in the policy analysis – phase 1

ST/ESSs	Indicator(s) from T2.2 29.06.2022 (SERENA M2.2, Foldal et al., 2022)
Soil erosion	soil loss in t ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹ by water erosion
	soil loss in t ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹ by wind erosion
	soil loss in t ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹ by tillage erosion
Soil organic carbon loss	SOC stock in t ha ⁻¹
	SOC concentration in g kg ⁻¹ (or %)
Nutrient imbalance	potential nutrients
	available nutrients
	ratio between two nutrients
	exchangeable cations
	different nutrients separately (N, P, K, S, Ca, Mg, Fe, Mn, Zn, Cu, B, Mo, Cl, Na, Si, Co, I, V)
	N content (N _{tot} , N _{min})
	available P, K, Ca, Mg
	micronutrients (B, Cu, Fe, Mn, S, Zn)
Soil acidification	pH-value
	base saturation; base cations in soil sorption complex; exchangeable Al content
Soil contamination	concentration of different contaminants: ppm; mg kg ⁻¹ soil
	diffuse pollution
	locations with (potential) soil contamination
	inorganic (Al, As, Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Hg, Ni, Pb, Zn, Mn, Fe, Ba)
	organic (PAHs, OCPs, PCBs) contaminants
Waterlogging	frequency/or days of occurrences of inland excess water; %
Soil sealing	percentage or hectare of sealed soil per year
	percentage of total surface of soil that is sealed
Soil compaction	porosity
	air-filled pore volume (%)
	bulk density
	permeability in g cm ⁻³ ; m s ⁻¹
	soil vulnerability to compaction
	risk level for soil compaction
	soil penetration resistance (curve)
Salinization	electrical conductivity (dS m ⁻¹) of soil saturation paste
	pH-value
Loss of diversity	soil invertebrates biodiversity index (QBS)
	soil microbial biomass carbon and functional groups
	density of earthworms occurrence

	biodiversity indices
	CLPP indicators
	CO ₂ efflux
	microbial biomass values
	enzymes activity
	potential mineralizable N
	invasive species and mortality
Biomass production	biomass (dry or wet) t ha ⁻¹ year ⁻¹
Habitat for biodiversity	diversity/richness
	abundance
	composition of above and belowground organisms
	presence/ absence invasive species
	rate of mortality
Erosion control	soil erosion rates in t ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹
	avoided soil loss in t ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹
	quantity of soil stabilised (not eroded) by the ecosystem
	area in which erosion is avoided or decreased
Hydrological control	frequency/or days of occurrences of inland excess water; %
Environmental pollution control	concentration of pollutants (ppm; mg kg ⁻¹ soil)
GHG and climate regulation/C sequestration	GHG emissions (CO ₂ fluxes, CH ₄ , N ₂ O) (t CO ₂ eqv. ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)
	Land Use (LU) change
	changes/increase in SOC stock
	Land Use Land Cover (LULC) change
	potential C sequestration
Pest and disease control	diversity/richness, abundance, composition of pests or antagonist and PGPOs (Plant Growth Promoting Organisms)
	fungi:bacteria
	presence/absence of invasive species
	mortality

Appendix 2. Indicators of ST/SES included in the stakeholders survey – phase 2

ST	Indicators (from the Task 1.2 questionnaire; Weninger et al., 2023)
Soil erosion	none
	Gully erosion (Number of observed gullies)
	Potential soil loss by water (t/ha/yr)
	Actual soil loss by water (t/ha/yr)
	Total (water, wind, tillage harvesting) soil loss (t/ha/yr)
	I don't know
Soil organic carbon loss	none
	SOC content/concentration (g/kg)
	SOC stock (kgC/ha)
	SOC stock change (kgC/ha/yr)
	SOC saturation (ratio of current SOC to the theoretical maximum potential)
	Risk of SOC deficiency (dimensionless)
	I don't know
Nutrient imbalance	none
	I don't know
	Certain thresholds, limits or target values.
Acidification	none
	pH-value
	base cations in soil sorption complex
	base saturation
	I don't know
Soil contamination	none
	Concentration of common contaminants
	I don't know
Waterlogging	none
	Frequency or number of days of occurrence of inland excess water
	frequency or number of days of occurrence of soil moisture excess
	I don't know
Soil compaction	none
	Degree of compaction (Ratio of current bulk density to reference bulk density)
	Change in bulk density (kg/m ³ /yr)
	Penetration resistance (MPa)
	Soil stress (Pressure applied on the soil by machinery)
	Vulnerability to compaction (dimensionless)
	Soil permeability (m/s)
	(Macro-)Porosity (cm ³ /cm ³)
	I don't know
Soil sealing	none
	Degree of soil sealing (Percentage of sealed soils in a particular area)
	Change in the degree of soil sealing (percent per year)
	Degree of imperviousness (Percentage of impervious soils in a particular area)
	Change in the degree of imperviousness (percent per year)
	Land take (Change in land use from natural, semi-natural, forest or agricultural areas to artificial surfaces)
	I don't know
Salinization	none

	Electrical conductivity of saturation extract
	Sodium adsorption ratio
	Content of Cl-ions
	I don't know
Loss of diversity	none
	Soil invertebrate richness (number of species)
	soil microbial biomass (mg C / kg soil) and functional groups
	microbial diversity (number of genes / ng of soil DNA)
	Earthworm abundance (number of individuals / m ²)
	earthworm species richness (number of species)
	I don't know
Soil drought	none
	Standard precipitation (-evapotranspiration) index
	Surface water supply index
	Rainfall anomaly index
	Soil moisture index
	I don't know
SES	Indicators (from the Task 1.2 questionnaire; Weninger et al., 2023)
Primary production	none
	Soil biomass productivity
	Potential NPP
	(total) Plant biomass
	Yields
	Net Energy Balance
	I don't know
Habitat for biodiversity	none
	Microbial biomass (mg kg ⁻¹)
	Microbial N (mg N kg ⁻¹)
	Microbial C (mg C kg ⁻¹)
	Diversity (number of taxa)
	Earthworm abundance (number of individuals / m ²)
	Soil basal respiration (CO ₂)
	SOC content/concentration (g kg ⁻¹)
	Bulk density (g / cm ³)
	I don't know
Erosion control	none
	Capacity of vegetation to reduce erosion risk (dimensionless)
	Decrease of erosion risk by vegetation (dimensionless)
	Capacity of vegetation to reduce soil losses (dimensionless)
	Total amount of soil not eroded (t ha ⁻¹ a ⁻¹)
	Surface area of natural vegetation with a function of erosion (dimensionless)
	I don't know
Hydrological control	none
	Infiltration capacity
	Groundwater recharge (dimensionless)
	Water yield (Annual amount of water that does not evapotranspire)
	Net water supply (Water supply minus water consumption for domestic purposes)
	Flood regulation supply (dimensionless)
	Water retention characteristics (available water capacity, field capacity)
	Saturated hydraulic conductivity (mm h ⁻¹)
	I don't know

Pollution control	none
	Concentration of various soil contaminants
	Quantity and quality of soil organic carbon
	Soil pH
	Clay mineral content
	Activity of soil microorganisms
	I don't know
Climate regulation	none
	Organic carbon stock in living plant materials (tC/ha)
	Soil organic carbon sequestration potential (tC ha ⁻¹)
	Soil organic carbon budget (tC ha ⁻¹ a ⁻¹)
	Net ecosystem productivity (Carbon assimilation by living materials minus soil respiration)
	Net soil greenhouse gas fluxes (Integration of CO ₂ sequestration and N ₂ O emissions)
	Greenhouse gas emissions from agricultural soils (div.)
	Changes in soil organic carbon stocks (tC ha ⁻¹ a ⁻¹)
	I don't know
Pest control	none
	Diversity/richnes
	Abundance
	Composition of pests or antagonist and Plant Growth Promoting Organisms
	Ratio fungi/bacteria
	Presence or absence of invasive species
	Mortality
	I don't know

Appendix 3. The detailed results of the review of the EU and international documents – phase 1.

Remark: the SERENA indicators mentioned in the document are marked in blue

ST/ESSs	SERENA indicator is already in the document (answer Yes)	assessment
UN Convention to Combat Desertification (5 indicators mentioned)		
Soil erosion	Soil loss by water and wind erosion	Only mentioned in general terms
Soil contamination	Diffuse pollution	Only mentioned in general terms
Salinization		Only mentioned in general terms
Loss of diversity		Only mentioned in general terms losses)
Biomass production		Only mentioned in general terms
Erosion control	Soil erosion rates, avoided soil loss	Only mentioned in general terms
GHG and climate regulation/C sequestration	Land Use Change/ Land Use Land Cover Change	Only mentioned in general terms
UN SDGs – SDG2 (12 indicators mentioned)		
Loss of diversity	Soil invertebrates biodiversity index (QBS)	
	Soil microbial biomass carbon and functional groups	
	Density of earthworms occurrence	
	Biodiversity indices	
	CLPP indicators	
	CO ₂ efflux	
	Microbial biomass values	
	Enzymes activity	
	Potential mineralizable N	
Biomass production	Total amount of biomass	In the context of supplying societies with food and feed
Habitat for biodiversity	Diversity	
Pest and disease control	Diversity/richness	Genetic variability
UN SDGs – SDG6 (6 indicators mentioned)		
Soil contamination	Contamination	
	Diffuse pollution	
	Locations with (potential) soil contamination	
	Inorganic contaminants	
	Organic contaminants	
Environmental pollution control	Concentration of pollutants	

UN SDGs – SDG13 (7 indicators mentioned)		
Soil organic carbon loss	SOC stock	
	SOC concentration	
Erosion control	Soil erosion rates	
	Avoided soil loss	
	quantity of soil stabilized (not eroded) by the ecosystem	
	Area in which erosion is avoided or decreased	
GHG and climate regulation/C sequestration	GHG emissions	
UN SDGs – SDG15 (43 indicators mentioned)		
Soil erosion	Soil loss by water/wind/tillage erosion	
Soil organic carbon loss	SOC stock	
	SOC concentration	
Soil contamination	Contamination	
	Diffuse pollution	
	Locations with soil contamination	
Soil sealing	Percentage or hectare of sealed soil per year	
	Percentage of total surface of soil that is sealed	
Salinization	Electrical conductivity	
	pH	
Loss of diversity	Soil invertebrates biodiversity index (QBS)	
	Soil microbial biomass carbon and functional groups	
	Density of earthworms occurrence	
	Biodiversity indices	
	CLPP indicators	
	CO ₂ efflux	
	Microbial biomass values	
	Enzymes activity	
	Potential mineralizable N	
	Invasive species	
Biomass production	Total amount of biomass	
Habitat for biodiversity	Diversity	
	Abundance	
	Composition of above and belowground organisms	
	Presence/absence invasive species	
	Rate of mortality	

Erosion control	Soil erosion rates	
	Avoided soil loss	
	Quantity of soil stabilised (not eroded) by the ecosystem	
	Area in which erosion is avoided or decreased	
Hydrological control	Frequency/or days of occurrences of inland excess water	
Environmental pollution control	Concentration of pollutants	
GHG and climate regulation/C sequestration	GHG emissions	
	Land Use Change	
	Changes/increase in SOC stock	
	Land Use Land Cover (LULC) Change	
	Potential C sequestration	
Pest and disease control	Diversity/richness, abundance, composition of pests	
	Fungi:bacteria	
	Presence/absence of invasive species	
	Mortality	
FAO-ITPS. Protocol for the assessment of Sustainable Soil Management (33 indicators mentioned)		
Soil erosion	Soil loss by water/wind/tillage erosion	
Soil organic carbon loss	SOC stock	Only mentioned in general terms
	SOC concentration	Organic carbon (%)
Nutrient imbalance	Available nutrients	
	Different nutrients separately	
	Available P, K, Ca, Mg	
Soil acidification	pH	Only mentioned in general terms (acidity and alkalinity)
Soil contamination	Concentration of different contaminants	Only mentioned in general terms
	Diffuse pollution	
Waterlogging	Frequency/or days of occurrences of inland excess water	Soil infiltration rate
Soil compaction	Porosity	
	Bulk density	
	Soil penetration resistance	
Salinization	Electrical conductivity	
Loss of diversity	Soil microbial biomass carbon and functional groups	
	Density of earthworms occurrence	
	Biodiversity indices	Soil respiration rate ($\text{gCO}_2\text{m}^{-2}\text{d}^{-1}$)
	Microbial biomass values	Soil microbial biomass

	Enzymes activity	
Biomass production	Biomass	Agricultural productivity or biomass in dry matter (t ha ⁻¹ year ⁻¹)
Habitat for biodiversity	Diversity/richness	Soil biological diversity
	Composition of above and belowground organisms	
Erosion control	Soil erosion rates	direct measurement of erosion in gullies, rills, sheet wash, landslides using erosion pins, sediment yield downhill or in drains using Gerlach boxes, or undercutting of the soils around trees and fence-lines
Hydrological control	Frequency/or days of occurrences of inland excess water	
Environmental pollution control	Concentration of pollutants	Only mentioned in general terms
GHG and climate regulation/C sequestration	GHG emissions	Only mentioned in general terms
	Land Use (LU) Change	
	Changes/increase in SOC stock	
	Land Use Land Cover (LULC) Change	
	Potential C sequestration	
Pest and disease control	Diversity/richness, abundance, composition of pests	
	Fungi:bacteria	
Recommendations of the EU Mission "Soil Health and Food" (26 indicators mentioned)		
Soil erosion	Soil loss by water/wind/tillage erosion	indicator is present in general form ('erosion' only) as soil health indicator
Soil organic carbon loss	SOC stock	
	SOC concentration	Not proposed as an soil health indicator but used in receiving mission targets
Nutrient imbalance	Different nutrients separately	
	N content	Not used as a term but as a general concept
	Available P, K, Ca, Mg	Not used as a term but is included in general principles
	Micronutrients	
Soil acidification	pH	
Soil contamination	Concentration of different contaminants	Soil health indicators considering pollutants are not specified
	Inorganic	
	Organic	
Soil sealing	Percentage or hectare of sealed soil per year	Not used as a term but is included in general principles
	Percentage of total surface of soil that is sealed	
Soil compaction	Bulk density	
Salinization	Electrical conductivity	Not specified, the term "excess of salts" as soil health indicator is used

Loss of diversity	Density of earthworms occurrence	
	Microbial biomass values	Soil health indicators for evaluating loss of biodiversity is not specified; it's noticed that ongoing research will soon deliver indicators for soil microbial parameters
Habitat for biodiversity	Diversity/richness	Soil health indicators for evaluating biodiversity is not specified; it's noticed that ongoing research will soon deliver indicators for soil microbial parameters
	Abundance	
Erosion control	Soil erosion rates	Not used as a term but is included in general principles
	Area in which erosion is avoided or decreased	
Environmental pollution control	Concentration of pollutants	
GHG and climate regulation/C sequestration	Changes/increase in SOC stock	
	Land Use Land Cover (LULC) change	
From Farm to Fork (7 indicators mentioned)		
Nutrient imbalance	Potential nutrients	The excess of nutrients (especially N and P) in the environment in general
	Different nutrients separately (N, P)	
Soil contamination	Organic contaminants	The use of pesticides in general
Loss of diversity	Biodiversity	`Biodiversity` is used as general term, not in the context of soil
Habitat for biodiversity		
Environmental pollution control		The use of pesticides in general, not specifying concentration as an indicator or detailed for soils
GHG and climate regulation/C sequestration	GHG emissions	
	Potential C sequestration	
Pest and disease control		Pest and disease control in general, not specifying indicators
Biodiversity Strategy (25 indicators mentioned)		
Soil erosion	Soil loss by water/wind/tillage erosion	indicator is present in general form ('erosion' only)
Soil organic carbon loss	SOC stock	carbon is present in general form; concept is carbon sequestration without specifying biomass or soil specifically
	SOC concentration	
Soil sealing	Percentage or hectare of sealed soil per year	the parameter is mentioned in the context of 'loss of habitat'
	Percentage of total surface of soil that is sealed	
Loss of diversity	Soil invertebrates biodiversity index (QBS)	biodiversity is not specified in detail and is not confined to 'soil'
	Soil microbial biomass carbon and functional groups	

	Density of earthworms occurrence	
	Biodiversity indices	
	CLPP indicators	
	CO ₂ efflux	
	Microbial biomass values	
	Enzymes activity	
	Potential mineralizable N	
	Invasive species	
Biomass production	Biomass	
Erosion control	Soil erosion rates	
	Avoided soil loss	
	quantity of soil stabilised (not eroded) by the ecosystem	
	Area in which erosion is avoided or decreased	
Environmental pollution control	Concentration of pollutants	the indicator is used in the context of water quality and filter capacity
GHG and climate regulation/C sequestration	Land Use (LU) change	used in the context of carbon sequestration in old growth forests
	Potential C sequestration	
European Climate Law (5 indicators mentioned)		
GHG and climate regulation/C sequestration	GHG emissions	
	Land Use (LU) change	
	Changes/increase in SOC stock	
	Land Use Land Cover (LULC) change	
	Potential C sequestration	
New Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) (8 indicators mentioned)		
Soil erosion		Soil erosion is present in the Objective 5 about Natural Resources, the related indicator is the % of agricultural area at risk of soil erosion (JRC, Impact indicator I.13)
Soil organic carbon loss	SOC stock	Organic carbon content is present in the Objective 4 about Climate Change, the related indicator is Mean organic carbon content (JRC, impact indicator I.12)
Nutrient imbalance		Nutrient imbalance is present in the Objective 5 about Natural Resources, the related indicators are the Gross nutrient balance in agricultural land and Nitrates in groundwater (EEA, impact indicators I.11)
	N content	
Soil acidification		Acidification is not present in the document, while it could be integrated to the Objective 5 about Natural Resources and mentioned in the document about efficient soil management
Soil contamination		Soil contamination is present in the Objective 9 about Food and Health Quality, the related

		indicators are Risks and impact of pesticides (DG SANTE), Sales of plant protection products (Eurostat), Farming intensity (DG AGRI, FADN) and Area under organic farming (Eurostat)
Waterlogging		Water is present in the Objective 5 about Natural Resources, the related indicator is the Water abstraction in agriculture (Eurostat, Impact indicators I.10, C.20)
Soil sealing		Soil sealing is not present in the Objectives, it could be included in Objective 6 about biodiversity and Ecosystem services. Soil sealing is mentioned in the "Efficient soil management" document
Soil compaction		Soil compaction is not present in the Objectives, it could be included in Objective 5 about Natural Resources. Soil compaction is mentioned in the "Efficient soil management" document
Salinization		Salinization is not present in the Objectives, it could be included in Objective 5 about Natural Resources. Salinization is mentioned in the "Efficient soil management" document
Loss of diversity	Biodiversity indexes	Biodiversity (in general) is present in the Objective 6 about Biodiversity and Ecosystem services, the related indicators are Farmland Bird Index (EBCC-PECBMS, Impact Indicator I.08), Conservation status of agricultural habitats (EEA-DG ENV, Context indicator C.36), Average number of linear elements (JRC) and Area under NATURA 2000 (NATURA 2000 Barometer, Context indicator C.34)
Biomass production		Biomass production is present in the Objectives 1 and 2 about Farm income and competitiveness, the related indicator is Total Factor Productivity (EBCC-PECBMS, Impact Indicator I.08)
Habitat for biodiversity	Abundance	Biodiversity (in general) is present in the Objective 6 about Biodiversity and Ecosystem services, the related indicators are Farmland Bird Index (EBCC-PECBMS, Impact Indicator I.08), Conservation status of agricultural habitats (EEA-DG ENV, Context indicator C.36), Average number of linear elements (JRC) and Area under NATURA 2000 (NATURA 2000 Barometer, Context indicator C.34)
	Rate of mortality	
Erosion control	Quantity of soil stabilised (not eroded) by the ecosystem	Soil erosion is present in the Objective 5 about Natural Resources, the related indicator is the % of agricultural area at risk of soil erosion (JRC, Impact indicator I.13)
Hydrological control	Frequency/or days of occurrences of inland excess water	Water is present in the Objective 5 about Natural Resources, the related indicator is the Water abstraction in agriculture (Eurostat, Impact indicators I.10, C.20)

Environmental pollution control		Soil contamination is present in the Objective 9 about Food and Health Quality, the related indicators are Risks and impact of pesticides (DG SANTE), Sales of plant protection products (Eurostat), Farming intensity (DG AGRI, FADN) and Area under organic farming (Eurostat)
GHG and climate regulation/C sequestration		Organic carbon content is present in the Objective 4 about Climate Change, the related indicator is Mean organic carbon content (JRC, impact indicator I.12)
4p1000 initiative (2 indicators mentioned)		
Soil organic carbon loss	carbon	This initiative focusses on Carbon market. The issue is on its website, but it does not include specific actions that have been carried out or are going to be carried out.
GHG and climate regulation/C sequestration		4x1000 is simply present in international forums. There are no publications available on its website.
EU Soil Strategy for 2030 (17 indicators mentioned)		
Soil organic carbon loss	Soil carbon stock	drainage of wetlands and organic soils should be limited in order to maintain and increase soil carbon stocks
	SOC concentration	actions are needed to preserve and increase organic carbon in mineral soils
Nutrient imbalance		'nutrient balance' is listed as one of the soil characteristics important for land users to implement best management practices; it can be included in soil testing systems for the 'Test your soil for free' initiative.
Soil acidification	pH	'pH' is listed as one of the soil characteristics important for land users to implement best management practices; it can be included in soil testing systems for the 'Test your soil for free' initiative.
Soil contamination	Concentration of contaminants	'preventing 'soil pollution' (both diffuse and point-source) at the source is a priority action to ensure clean and healthy soils; this action should include: more efficient fertilizers application, reduction of the use and risk of pesticides and antimicrobials, restrictions on micro-plastics and PFAS.
	Diffuse pollution	
	Locations with soil contamination	"number and location of contaminated sites" are important to identify and maintain a register for contaminated sites by MS, assess the risk and to remediate such sites
Soil sealing		terms 'soil sealing and land take'; Member States should set target to reduce net land take by 2030; definition of 'net land take' will be provided in Soil Health Law; possible monitoring and reporting on progress towards the no land take targets and the implementation land take

		hierarchy; there is a need to provide guidance on how to reduce soil sealing
Soil compaction	Bulk density	'bulk density' is listed as one of the soil characteristics important for land users to implement best management practices; it can be included in soil testing systems for the 'Test your soil for free' initiative.
Loss of diversity	Biodiversity	general term "biodiversity"; the need to increase biodiversity on agricultural land was identified, which would contribute to conserving and increasing the amount of organic carbon in the soil; announcement of the first assessment of EU soil biodiversity and antimicrobial resistant genes in agricultural soils under different management regimes
	Invasive species	term 'invasive alien species' was mentioned as a threat to soil biodiversity
Biomass production		'provide food and biomass production' is listed among the mentioned ecosystem services
Habitat for biodiversity	Diversity	general term of ecosystem service 'the basis for life and biodiversity, including habitats, species and genes' and general term 'biodiversity'
	Composition of above and belowground organisms	general term 'soil organisms' is used in the context of their protection and preservation
	Presence/ absence invasive species	term 'invasive alien species' was mentioned as a threat to soil biodiversity
Environmental pollution control		there is a need to prevent soil pollution (diffuse and point-source) at the source and to reduce the release the hazardous substances into environment, including soils
GHG and climate regulation/C sequestration	GHG emissions	net-zero greenhouse gas emission should be achieved by 2050; limiting drainage and restoring drained organic soils to reduce CO2 emissions from land;
	Changes/increase in SOC stock	drainage of wetlands and organic soils should be limited in order to maintain and increase soil carbon stocks and prevent CO2 emissions
	Potential C sequestration	carbon sequestration in mineral soils as a cost-effective emission mitigation method
Pest and disease control	Presence/absence of invasive species	term 'invasive alien species' was mentioned as a threat to soil biodiversity
EU Action Plan for the Circular Economy (3 indicators mentioned)		
Soil sealing	Soil sealing	
Environmental pollution control	Environmental footprints, environmental impacts	refers to "environmental pressures", and concerning to indicators refers to: "Indicators on resource use, including consumption and material footprints to account for material consumption and environmental impacts associated to our production and consumption patterns will also be further developed and will be linked to monitoring and assessing the progress towards decoupling economic growth

		from resource use and its impacts in the EU and beyond."
GHG and climate regulation/C sequestration	Carbon farming sequestration	The Commission will consider establishing sustainability principles and other appropriate ways to regulate carbon farming sequestration and will promote circularity principles in carbon reduction principles and carbon storage.
Environmental Liability Directive (0)		
Soil contamination	No indicator is provided in this directive, but the idea is to remedy pollution, including soil pollution.	
Industrial Emissions Directive (0)		
Soil contamination	No specific indicator is included in the EID Directive; the Directive indicates the need to prevent, limit and control emissions to air, water and soil and to monitor the state of the soil in relation to hazardous substances that will be used, produced or released as a result of the operation of industrial installations.	
EU Forest Strategy (30 indicators mentioned)		
Soil erosion	Soil loss by water/wind/tillage erosion	implicitly included via 'forest restoration' which per se includes the prevention of soil erosion
Soil organic carbon loss	SOC stock	implicitly included via the expected sequestration of carbon in forest soils and carbon farming (p. 19)
	SOC concentration	
Soil acidification	pH	in the context of forest restoration
Soil compaction		soil compaction is mentioned on p 12 as potential problem. No specific indicator is listed
Loss of diversity	Soil invertebrates biodiversity index (QBS)	no clear distinction between forest soil, forest stand, landscape level
	Soil microbial biomass carbon and functional groups	
	Density of earthworms occurrence	
	Biodiversity indices	
	CLPP indicators	
	CO ₂ efflux	
	Microbial biomass values	
	Enzymes activity	
	Potential mineralizable N	
	Invasive species	invasive species are a paramount topic
Habitat for biodiversity	Diversity/richness	
	Abundance	
	Composition of above and belowground organisms	
	Presence/absence invasive species	
	Rate of mortality	
Erosion control	Soil erosion rates	
	Avoided soil loss	

	Quantity of soil stabilised (not eroded) by the ecosystem	
	Area in which erosion is avoided or decreased	
Hydrological control	Frequency/or days of occurrences of inland excess water	
GHG and climate regulation/C sequestration	GHG emissions	
	Potential C sequestration	
Pest and disease control	Presence/absence of invasive species	
	Mortality	
Nitrate Directive (0)		
Soil contamination	The objective of the Nitrate Directive is not to provide elements related to soil, but to water. Nevertheless, there is a limit concerning the Nitrate content of livestock manure, which must be less than 170 kg N/ha/year (then, not a soil concentration but a manure concentration)	

